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and thiazole-2-malonamic acid with salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehydes using trace of pyridine or piperidine as condensing agent. Some of the coumarins and Schiff's bases synthesised have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity. Some earlier workers have reported the chemotherapeutic value⁴⁻⁷ of coumarins and Schiff's bases.

Some New Coumarins and Schiff's Bases as Possible Antibacterial and Antifungal Agents

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Experimental

Condensation of Malon-3-chloro-2-methoxy anilic acid with Salicylaldehyde : Formation of Coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methoxy) anilide and 2-hydroxy benzal (3-chloro-2-methoxy) aniline :

Malon-3-chloro-2-methoxy anilic acid (1.2 g), salicylaldehyde (0.6 g) and a drop of pyridine were heated in an oil bath at 80° for four hrs. The yellow solid mass was then digested with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (10 ml). The alkali extract was decanted and the residue washed well with water. The alkali extract on acidification with HCl (conc.) did not form any precipitate. The residue was then boiled with ethanol (15 ml) and

IN our earlier communications we described the preparation of some new malon anilic acids^{1, 2}, coumarins and Schiff's bases³. The present paper deals with the synthesis of some new coumarins and Schiff's bases by condensing malon *o*-pheneticid, 3-chloro-2-methyl, 3-chloro-2-methoxy anilic acids

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. (°C)	Nitrogen%		m.p. (°C)	Nitrogen%	
					Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.
1.	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₄ -	H	H	200	4.39	4.53	—	—	—
2.	"	Cl	H	218	3.92	4.07	98	4.94	5.08
3.	"	Cl	Cl	233	3.78	3.70	84	4.45	4.51
4.	"	Br	H	207	3.80	3.60	87	4.30	4.37
5.	"	Br	Br	220	2.79	2.99	108	3.26	3.50
6.	"	I	I	267	2.11	2.49	150	2.93	2.84
7.	"	H	NO ₂	232	8.47	7.91	128	9.14	9.79
8.	"	NO ₂	NO ₂	278	10.25	10.52	250	12.23	12.69
9.	3-Cl-2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ -	H	H	232	4.40	4.46	103	5.35	5.70
10.	3-Cl-2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ -	Cl	H	252	3.45	4.02	102	5.63	5.00
11.	"	Cl	Cl	288	3.48	3.65	146	4.92	4.45
12.	"	Br	H	237	3.38	3.56	105	4.33	4.31
13.	"	Br	Br	224	3.27	2.96	151	3.37	3.46
14.	"	I	I	202	2.62	2.47	196	2.59	2.81
15.	"	NO ₂	H	268	7.17	7.81	185	9.52	9.64
16.	3-Cl-2-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃ -	Cl	H	253	3.50	3.85	118	4.69	4.74
17.	"	Cl	Cl	262	3.68	3.52	121	4.05	4.24
18.	"	Br	H	238	2.95	3.42	105	3.63	4.11
19.	"	Br	Br	214	2.26	2.87	109	3.20	3.33
20.	"	I	I	251	1.95	2.40	69	2.46	2.72
21.	"	NO ₂	H	277	7.31	7.47	176	8.61	9.13
22.	"	Cl	NO ₂	261	7.15	6.86	212	8.88	8.23
23.	C ₆ H ₄ NS(2')	Cl	H	205	9.04	9.14	128	11.68	11.74
24.	"	Cl	Cl	214	7.58	8.23	108	10.10	10.29
25.	C ₆ H ₄ NS(2')	Br	H	202	7.37	7.97	114	9.27	9.89
26.	"	Br	Br	194	6.73	6.51	148	7.51	7.77
27.	"	I	I	—	—	—	187	6.53	6.14
28.	"	NO ₂	H	226	12.92	13.24	198	17.20	16.86

1. All the melting points are taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.
 2. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and halogen/sulphur analyses.

NOTES

filtered hot. The yellow solid left was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid and was identified to be coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methoxy) anilide (A) m.p. 238°, yield 0.94 g (58.02%).

(Found : C, 62.20% ; H, 3.88% ; N, 4.51% ; Cl, 10.56% ; Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{12}O_4NCl$; C, 61.91% ; H, 3.64% ; N, 4.24% ; Cl, 10.77%).

The ethanolic extract was concentrated and on cooling gave 0.32 g (25%) of 2-hydroxy benzal (3-chloro-2-methoxy) aniline (B), m.p. 54°.

(Found : C, 65.00% ; H, 5.15% ; N, 5.26% ; Cl, 13.48% ; Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}O_2NCl$, C, 64.24% ; H, 4.58% ; N, 5.35% ; Cl, 13.57%).

The identity of this product was further confirmed by synthesising an authentic specimen from 3-chloro-2-methoxy aniline and salicylaldehyde.

The substituted salicylaldehydes were condensed with different malon anilic acids in the same manner and the product extracted as described above. The effect of different condensing agents was also studied. The coumarins and Schiff's bases obtained along with their analytical results m.p. are recorded in the Table 1.

Antibacterial and Antifungal Activity Test :

Some of the coumarins and Schiff's bases synthesised have been tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity "in vitro".

It was found that 6-bromo-coumarin-*o*-phenetide was active against the bacteria *B. subtilis* (activity = 6.25 r/ml), and the fungi *T. mentagrophytes* (activity = 50 r/ml), *A. niger* (activity = 50 r/ml), 6-chloro-coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methyl) anilide active against the bacteria *S. aureus* (activity = 12.5 r/ml), *B. subtilis* (activity = 6.25 r/ml) and the fungi *A. niger* (activity = 50 r/ml), 6 : 8-dibromo-coumarin-3-carboxy (3-chloro-2-methoxy) anilide active against the bacteria *V. comma* (activity = 200 r/ml) and the fungi *T. rubrum* (activity = 200 r/ml) and 5-chloro-2-hydroxy-benzal-2'-aminothiazole active against the fungi *C. albicans* (activity = 200 r/ml) and the rest of the compounds were found to be inactive.

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Chemical Constituents of *Psidium guava* Heartwood

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THE wood of *Psidium guava* tree, although not an important timber, is still used for making some instruments specially spear handles; the stem bark of this plant has been worked up in the past for its polyphenols¹.

The shavings of the heartwood were extracted with boiling ethanol and the concentrated extract fractionated into (I) light petrol, (II) ether and (III) ethylacetate soluble fractions. Fractions I and II furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 138° and gallic acid, m.p. 253° (dec), along with small amount of quercetin respectively, which were identified by comparison (ir, mmp and Co-TLC) with authentic samples. Fraction (III) was a mixture of three compounds. This fraction on concentration and standing at low temperature for a few days, deposited white shining crystals, m.p. 308°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 76^\circ$ (CHCl₃). This gave positive colour reactions for triterpenoids, formed monoacetate m.p. 266°, and insoluble salt with KOH and methylester m.p. 198°. This was finally confirmed as oleanolic acid by superimposable ir spectrum and undepressed mmp with an authentic sample. The mother liquor after removal of oleanolic acid was chromatographed over silica gel column to give two compounds. One of these, a buff coloured semicrystalline solid on boiling with ethanolic-HCl gave cyanidin, $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH/HCl}$ (nm) 540. It had λ_{\max}^{EtOH} (nm) 280 and ir

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